

ENHANCED DIELECTRIC PROPERTIES IN A THREE-PHASE COMPOSITE INDUCED BY MICROSTRUCTURE TAILORING

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ABSTRACT

Polymer-matrix composites with excellent dielectric property have attracted great attentions due to their various potential applications, such as electrostatic energy storage device, embedded capacitors, actuators, and printed circuit boards. In general, for polymer filled by conductive and semi-conductive filler, a very high dielectric permittivity can be obtained at low filler loading. However, there are still some obstacles, such as high dielectric loss, high electrical conductivity and narrow processing window, which largely inhibit their practical applications. In this paper, a novel three-phase composite is proposed to achieve by introducing nano-size and micro-size barium titanate (BT) as an insulating phase in polyvinylidene fluoride (PVDF) matrix composite filled by semi-conductive silicon carbide whiskers (SiC). In the as-prepared SiC/PVDF two-phase composite, Scanning electron micrograph shows that a semi-conductive network of SiC whisker can be formed at the filler loading of 20 vol%. The dielectric permittivity can be increased to 396.6 with a high dielectric loss of 6.2 at testing frequency of 100 Hz. After the introduction of BT particles, the nano-size BT can be homogeneously distributed in the matrix and prevents the formation of the SiC whisker semi-conductive network. Thus, it is found that the BT/SiC/PVDF three-phase composite presents a greatly suppressed dielectric loss of 0.27 while a high dielectric permittivity of 213.8 is maintained filled with 15 vol% of nano-size BT. Additionally, further research demonstrates that the interfacial polarization process and electron conduction process in two-phase composite can be greatly enhanced by the semi-conductive network of SiC whisker and results in high dielectric permittivity and dielectric loss. The addition of BT, which effectively prevents the formation of semi-conductive networks, greatly restricts the electron conduction process. Therefore the high dielectric loss in three-phase composites can be suppressed at a very low value while a high dielectric permittivity is still maintained.

1 INTRODUCTION

Polymer-matrix composites with excellent dielectric property have attracted great attentions due to their various potential applications, such as embedded capacitors, actuators, and printed circuit boards [1-3]. For polymer filled by ceramic filler with high dielectric property, the dielectric permittivity can be increased by more than 10-20 times [4-5]. However, the loading of ceramic filler is usually required no less than 50 vol. %, which subjects the composite to several inevitable limitations, such as low flexibility and difficult processing [4]. On the other hand, for polymer filled by conductive and semi-conductive filler, a very high dielectric permittivity can be obtained at low filler loading near percolation threshold, which is usually below 16 vol. %. However, high dielectric loss and electrical conductivity caused by semi-conductive and conductive network lead to severe problems including

high energy loss and overheating, which are undesirable for practical applications [6]. Thus, the key issue lies in increasing dielectric permittivity and retaining low dielectric loss and electrical conductivity for this kind of composite with appropriate filler loading of dielectric filler.

Several strategies have been developed to reduce dielectric loss and electrical conductivity of polymer composites with high dielectric permittivity. One common method is to employ surfactants, such as silane coupling agent, phosphate esters and oligomers, which yield low dielectric loss by eradicating ceramic filler agglomerations, voids and improving the interfacial compatibility between fillers and matrix [7-9]. Unfortunately, the residual free surfactant usually causes high leakage current that deteriorates the insulation property of the composite. Another alternative approach is to disperse ceramic fillers with core-shell microstructure in matrix to fabricating dielectric composite. The shell layer not only benefits for homogeneous dispersion of fillers in matrix, but also acts as an effective barrier retarding the movement of charge carriers in the composite. This method can result in obvious improvements in integrative dielectric and insulation properties [10-13]. However, the fabrication of core-shell structure filler usually needs expensive chemical precursor and time-consuming multiple-step synthesis.

Recently, a few studies focus on introducing an insulating phase in a two-phase composite consisting of a semi-conductive/conductive phase and polymer phase, so high dielectric permittivity and reduced dielectric loss in the three-phase composite can be obtained [14-18]. Li M et al reported a three-phase composite with enhanced dielectric performance by introducing Al flakes into Bi₂S₃/PVDF matrix. The low dielectric loss in the three-phase composite was attributed to the insulating effect of the self-passive Al flakes perpendicular to AC electric field on the leakage current [19]. A flexible polyimide-graphene-BT composite fabricated by Liu J et al showed excellent dielectric permittivity and largely suppressed dielectric loss due to the isolation effect of BT particles on graphene agglomeration [20]. Different conductive filler, polymer matrix and insulating filler in three-phase composites result in different dielectric polarization and dielectric relaxation mechanism, which further determine their dielectric and electrical properties. Therefore, this three-phase polymer composite is believed to be an effective and flexible method for tailoring dielectric properties and overcoming the limitations of traditional two-phase polymer composites [4].

The β -silicon carbide (SiC) is a nonoxide semi-conductive ceramic with high dielectric permittivity, excellent oxidation resistance and relatively low density [21-22]. Its whisker is more favored as dielectric filler in achieving higher dielectric permittivity of composite compared with spherical and flake shaped fillers [23-24]. Polar poly(vinylidene fluoride) (PVDF) is a polymer with high dielectric permittivity and good flexibility [25]. PVDF polymer filled with 1-D SiC whiskers are likely to exhibit high dielectric permittivity at low filler loading with low packaging density. However, dielectric loss and electrical conductivity in the composite are also high due to the semi-conductive property of SiC fillers. Based on the concept of the three-phase composite above-mentioned, it is anticipated that the dielectric and electrical properties of the two-phase SiC/PVDF composite can be improved by introducing secondary filler acting as an insulating phase.

In this paper, microstructure and properties of the composite consisting of SiC whiskers and PVDF were changed by introducing BT particle as secondary filler. Dielectric properties of the composites with and without BT particle were investigated. The filler loading and size effect of BT particles on the properties of the three-phase composite were studied by respectively using nano-size and micro-size BT particles. The dielectric polarization process and relaxation behaviors with and without BT particle were studied by means of electric modulus formalism.

2 EXPERIMENTAL DETAILS

2.1 MATERIALS

All materials in this study are commercially available. Raw silicon carbide whiskers were purchased from Xuzhou Jiechuang New Material Technology Co., Ltd. It has an average diameter of

500 nm-1 μm and approximate length/diameter ratio over 40. Two kinds of BT particles with average diameter of 100 nm and 1 μm respectively were purchased from Aladdin Industrial Inc. FR904 PVDF powders were purchased from the Shanghai 3F Company. The DMF solvent with chemical purity of 99% was purchased from Xilong chemical Inc.

2.2 FABRICATION OF COMPOSITE

The PVDF was dissolved in the DMF solvent with a mass ratio of 1:40 by stirring at 60 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ to acquire a transparent diluent. For the fabrication of SiC/PVDF two-phase composite, a certain amount of SiC whisker (5 vol. %, 10 vol. %, 15 vol. %, 20 vol. %) was added in the as-prepared diluent. For the fabrication of BT/SiC/PVDF three-phase composite, a fixed amount of SiC whisker (20 vol. %) and various amount of BT particles (5 vol. %, 10 vol. %, 15 vol. %, 20 vol. %) were added in the as-prepared diluent. The obtained mixture was treated by 3h of ultrasonication and followed by 3h of stirring to form a stable suspension. Then, the suspension was cast on a smooth glass mold and held for 1h at 60 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ to obtain composite film with an average thickness of 30-50 μm . In order to measure dielectric and electrical properties, 30-50 layers of films were firstly stacked from bottom to top, and then placed between two smooth molds. The stacked films were hot-pressed into a bulk material at 200 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ under 10 MPa (prepressed for 30 min at the same temperature, released the press for 15 min, and then repressed for 30 min, followed by cooling to room temperature under the same pressure). The bulk material was further pruned into a 10 mm \times 10 mm flake with 2 mm thickness. Silver electrodes were painted on both sides of the flake in order to perform dielectric measurements.

2.3 CHARACTERIZATION

X-ray diffraction measurements were carried out with Cu K α 1 between scattering angles in the range of 10-80 $^{\circ}$ (Rigaku D/MAX-2200 diffractometer, Japan). The images of cross fracture of composite flake samples were investigated by scanning electron microscopy (SEM, JEOL 7500). Dielectric permittivity, dielectric loss, AC conductivity of the composite were measured by means of Agilent 4294A impedance analyzer at the frequency range of 10²-10⁶ Hz at room temperature under applied voltage of 500 mV. The electric modulus of the studied composite was tested using a Solartron SI 1260 impedance analyzer (Advanced Measurement Technology, Inc., Wokingham, U.K.) at the frequency range of 10⁻² to 10⁶ Hz at ambient temperature under applied voltage of 500 mV.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 MORPHOLOGY AND MICROSTRUCTURES

X-ray diffraction analysis was carried out to study the crystalline structure of the polymer, SiC/PVDF and nano-size BT/SiC/PVDF. Fig. 1 shows XRD patterns of pure PVDF, SiC/PVDF and nano-size BT/SiC/PVDF. It is observed that 2 Theta degrees of 18.4 $^{\circ}$ and 20.5 $^{\circ}$ refer to the plane of (020) and (200) for α -phase and β -phase PVDF, respectively. Four peaks at 2 Theta degrees of 35.64 $^{\circ}$, 41.35 $^{\circ}$, 60.00 $^{\circ}$ and 71.95 $^{\circ}$ corresponding to the plane of (111), (200), (220) and (311) can be observed and indexed in the patterns of SiC whisker. The peaks in Fig.1 at 2Theta degrees of 22.1 $^{\circ}$, 31.5 $^{\circ}$, 38.9 $^{\circ}$, 45.3 $^{\circ}$, 51 $^{\circ}$, and 56.3 $^{\circ}$ corresponding to the plane of (100), (110), (111), (200), (210), and (211) can be observed and indexed in the patterns of nano-size BT. It can be seen that the crystal structure of the PVDF is not obviously affected by the addition of the SiC whiskers. However, the crystalline phases of PVDF matrix are found to be largely influenced by the introduction of BT. Both the peaks at (020) and (200) representing α -phase and β -phase of PVDF matrix decrease with the increase of BT filler loading, which might indicate the suppressive effect of distributed BT filler on formation of α -phase and β -phase PVDF.

Fig. 1. XRD patterns of Pure PVDF, SiC/PVDF with different filler loading of SiC and BT/SiC/PVDF with different filler loading of nano-size BT.

Fig.2 (a-b) shows the cross fracture images of SiC/PVDF two-phase composite flake samples with different filler loading. It can be seen that SiC whiskers are well dispersed in the matrix randomly without serious aggregation. However, as the filler loading continues to increase, SiC whiskers intend to contact and overlap with each other as marked by red circles shown in Fig.2 (b). The cross fracture images of BT/SiC/PVDF three-phase composite flake samples with different filler loading of nano-size BT displayed in Fig.2 (c-d) clearly show that both BT particles and SiC whiskers are homogeneously distributed in the matrix. Furthermore, the SiC whiskers are effectively isolated by BT in the PVDF matrix. This isolation effect is expected to be beneficial in achieving low dielectric loss and AC conductivity with high dielectric permittivity. However, as the filler loading reaches 20 vol.%, the aggregation of BT particles and porosity observed are marked by red circles as shown in Fig.2 (d), which would deteriorate dielectric and electrical properties of the composite [4].

Fig. 2. SEM images of cross fracture of SiC/PVDF composites with SiC filler loading of (a) 10 vol. %, (b) 20 vol. % and BT/SiC/PVDF composites with nano-BT filler loading of (c) 10 vol. %, (d) 20 vol. %.

3.2 DIELECTRIC PROPERTIES OF TWO-PHASE COMPOSITE

The dielectric permittivity and dielectric loss as functions of the frequency at different SiC filler loading are shown in Fig.3. At filler loading below 15 vol. %, the dielectric permittivity gradually decrease with the increase of frequency. However, the dielectric permittivity and dielectric loss are found to decrease rapidly with the increase of frequency at 20 vol. %. The observed strong frequency dependence indicates strong interfacial polarization and electron conduction process. When the SiC whisker is introduced in the PVDF, the large differences in both dielectric and electrical properties between the matrix and filler cause strong interfacial polarization process [27, 28]. Thus, both the dielectric permittivity and dielectric loss of the composite gradually increase with the increase of SiC whisker loading [24]. Furthermore, when the filler loading increases to 20 vol. %, it is speculated that a semi-conductive network of SiC whisker is formed throughout the composite. The semi-conductive network greatly facilitates the accumulation of charge carriers at the interface and electron conduction process in the composite, which result in a sharp increase in dielectric permittivity and dielectric loss with a strong frequency dependence.

Fig. 3. Frequency dependence of (a) dielectric permittivity and (b) dielectric loss for SiC-W/PVDF with different SiC filler loading.

3.3 DIELECTRIC PROPERTIES OF THREE-PHASE COMPOSITE

To counter the high dielectric loss of the two-phase composite, the nano-size BT particles were introduced as an insulating phase to lower the dielectric loss of the composite.

The frequency dependence of the dielectric permittivity and dielectric loss of the BT/SiC/PVDF three-phase composite with different filler loading of BT are displayed in Fig.4 (a) and (b). It is shown that with the increase of BT loading, the dielectric loss of the composite greatly reduces while the dielectric permittivity remains relatively high. At 15 vol. % of BT, the dielectric permittivity decreases from 396.6 to 213.8, while the dielectric loss drops from 6.2 to 0.27 (@100Hz). It is speculated that the introduction of BT particles successfully inhibit the direct connection and overlapping of SiC whiskers, as shown in Fig2. (c-d), which in turn significantly lower the dielectric loss. In addition, the dielectric loss increases slightly as the BT loading reaches 20 vol.%, while the dielectric permittivity continues to decrease due to the aggregation of BT particles and porosity.

Fig. 4. Frequency dependence of (a) dielectric permittivity and (b) dielectric loss for BT/SiC-W/PVDF with different filler loading of nano-size BT.

3.4 SIZE EFFECT OF BT ON DIELECTRIC PROPERTIES OF THREE-PHASE COMPOSITE

Fillers with different particle sizes are found to affect dielectric properties of polymer composites

[29]. In order to analyze the size effect of BT particle on the dielectric properties of the three-phase composite, the comparative tests were carried out by respectively employing BT of 100nm and 1 μ m at the same filler loading of 15 vol. %. The variations of dielectric permittivity and dielectric loss as functions of frequency are displayed in Fig.5 (a) and (b). It is revealed that the composite filled with nano-size BT possess higher dielectric permittivity and slightly lower dielectric loss in the low frequency range than the composite filled with micro-size BT particles. It is supposed that the dielectric permittivity of three-phase composite is mainly contributed by the strong interfacial polarization in the interfaces of SiC, BT and PVDF due to their large differences in dielectric and electrical properties [16]. The nano-size BT with large specific surface area is more beneficial in increasing interface area compared with the micro-size BT. As a result, the nano-size BT is more favored in enhancing interfacial polarization process and higher dielectric permittivity is achieved. In the case of dielectric loss, BT particles seem to not only destroy the networks but also somewhat improve the dispersion of SiC whiskers with appropriate filler loading and size [14]. It is supposed that at the same filler loading, compared with micro-size BT, more nano-size BT can be better fitted in the narrow gaps between adjacent SiC whiskers to block the network and improve the dispersion of SiC whiskers (see Fig.2 (c) and Fig.5 (c)). Thus a lower dielectric loss in the three-phase composite can be obtained.

Fig. 5. Frequency dependence of (a) dielectric permittivity, (b) dielectric loss for BT/SiC/PVDF with different BT and (c) SEM images of cross fracture of BT/SiC/PVDF with 15 vol. % of micro-size BT.

3.5 DIELECTRIC POLARIZATION PROCESS AND RELAXATION BEHAVIORS OF THE COMPOSITES

For better understanding of the dielectric polarization and relaxation behaviors in the studied composites and the role of BT particle as insulating filler, the frequency-dependent electric modulus formalism was studied. Since the real part M' of the complex M^* , by its definition, is inversely proportional with dielectric permittivity. Its reciprocal, $1/M'$ is used to represent the frequency-dependent dielectric polarization process. The value of imaginary part of M'' of the complex electric modulus M^* , is used to interpret the frequency-dependent dielectric relaxation process.

Fig. 6. Frequency dependence of (a) $1/M'$ and (b) M'' for SiC/PVDF with different SiC filler loading .

The frequency dependence of $1/M'$ of the two-phase composite with different filler loading of SiC whisker is displayed in Fig.6 (a). It can be seen that the value of $1/M'$ increases and the frequency dependence becomes stronger as the filler loading increases. This clearly indicates that compared with pure PVDF, a strong interfacial polarization process is induced by the introduction of SiC whisker. Furthermore, as the filler loading reaches 20 vol. %, the interfacial polarization becomes enormously intense due to the formation of semi-conductive network, resulting in a very high dielectric permittivity with strong frequency-dependence.

The frequency dependence of the imaginary part M'' in the two-phase composite on the filler loading is shown in Fig. 6 (b). Two major dielectric relaxation peaks can be observed in pure PVDF. The relaxation peak in high frequency range ($>10^5\text{Hz}$) represents the dipole polarization process attributed to the molecular movements in the crystalline region of PVDF [24]. The dielectric relaxation peak in low frequency range represents the dielectric loss attributed to the conduction process of electron on the boundary between the lamellar crystal and interlamellar amorphous region and interfacial polarization process. Compared to the pure PVDF, the addition of SiC whisker as shown in Fig.2 (a) greatly enhances the interfacial polarization and electron conduction process by introducing heterogeneous SiC-PVDF interface [27-29]. As a result, the dielectric relaxation peaks become weaker, broader and shift to higher frequency range as the filler loading increases. As the filler loading becomes high, the SiC whiskers come into direct contact with each other as shown in Fig.2 (b). A semi-conductive network within the composite is formed at 20 vol. %, so the electron conduction process within the whole frequency range is enhanced. The dielectric relaxation peak then moves to much high frequency range which cannot be seen due to the limitation of the testing conditions as shown in Fig.6 (b) and leads to very high frequency-dependent dielectric loss (see Fig.3 (b)).

Fig. 7. Frequency dependence of (a) $1/M'$ and (b) M'' for BT/SiC/PVDF with different filler loading of nano-size BT.

The frequency dependence of $1/M'$ of three-phase composite with different filler loading of nano-size BT is displayed in Fig.7 (a). The value of $1/M'$ gradually decreases and shows weaker frequency dependence with the increase of BT. This indicates that the interfacial polarization strength is gradually weakened due to the introduction of BT. Moreover; the interfacial polarization strength is still high enough at 15 vol. % of BT to yield high dielectric permittivity in the three-phase composite. As the filler loading of BT reaches 20 vol. %, the aggregation of BT particles and porosity observed in Fig.2 (d) lead to obvious deterioration in interfacial polarization process, resulting in the decrease of $1/M'$.

The frequency dependence of the imaginary part M'' of the three-phase composite with different filler loading of nano-size BT is displayed in Fig.7 (b). It can be clearly observed that a major dielectric relaxation peak emerges after the addition of BT and moves to lower frequency range as the filler loading increases. The reason can be explained by the isolation effect of BT particles on the semi-conductive network. The BT particles with appropriate filler loading can be dispersed homogeneously in the matrix and thus effectively inhibit the formation of SiC semi-conductive network, as shown in Fig.2 (c). In such a case, the dielectric loss can be largely decreased as a result of greatly suppressed conduction process of charge carriers and space charges [29]. However, as the filler loading increases to 20 vol. %, the dielectric relaxation peak stops shifting towards lower frequency. It is assumed that the agglomeration of BT as shown in Fig.2 (d) facilitates the electron conduction process and leads to the increase in dielectric loss.

The introduction of BT particles plays a key role in property enhancement by changing the microstructure of three-phase composite. The strong frequency-dependent interfacial polarization process can be moderately inhibited (see Fig. 7(a)) to yield a high dielectric permittivity with improved frequency-stability. The intensive electron conduction process can be greatly restricted (see Fig. 7(b)) which results in largely suppressed dielectric loss and AC conductivity. It is shown that, as an insulating phase, the filler loading and particle size of BT affects the properties of three-phase composite to a large extent. An appropriate filler loading, for example, 15 vol. % is required for BT particles to effectively block the network and improves the distribution of SiC whiskers. However, a higher filler loading, 20 vol. % for instance, may deteriorate the properties by causing agglomerations and porosities as shown in Fig.2 (d). The three-phase composite with 20 vol. % of SiC whiskers and 15 vol. % of nano-size BT exhibits improved dielectric permittivity of 213.8 and dielectric loss of 0.27 at 100 Hz. Compared to other composites with high dielectric permittivity, the as-prepared three-phase composite possess much lower dielectric loss attributed to its unique microstructure. Moreover, SiC whisker with a light packing density (3.12 g/cm³), good thermal stability and high thermal

conductivity is believed to be favorable used as dielectric fillers [24].

4 CONCLUSIONS

A polymer composite with high dielectric permittivity was prepared by embedding SiC whisker in PVDF. However, the composite also yields high dielectric loss and electrical conductivity due to the semi-conductive network of SiC whiskers. BT particles were introduced as an insulating phase into SiC/PVDF two-phase composite, which is proved to be beneficial in dielectric and electrical properties. The morphological analysis indicates that the BT can be uniformly distributed between adjacent SiC whiskers and block the networks. Compared with two-phase composite, the three-phase BT/SiC/PVDF composite shows dramatically suppressed dielectric loss with improved frequency stability. When the filler loading of nano-size BT is 15 vol. %, the network of SiC whiskers can be blocked and uniform dispersion of SiC whiskers in matrix can be realized. Thus the dielectric permittivity enhances significantly with the dielectric loss decreasing abruptly. It also shows that nano-size BT is more favorable in achieving high dielectric permittivity due to larger interfaces than micro-size BT. Furthermore, the electric modulus formalism is applied to describe the dielectric polarization process and relaxation behaviors of the composites.

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